

Prompt 02: Geração de Cenários de Teste

Given one or more non-functional requirements, generate test scenarios that verify the system's compliance with those requirements. Each scenario should describe a concrete and observable situation of system use, which may involve variations in load, failures, exceptions, or human interactions. The scenarios should be objective, based on realistic context, and cover both expected behavior and tolerable limits and failures. Consider creating multiple scenarios per requirement, addressing different conditions and checkpoints relevant to the described quality.